

D1.3. Innovation and Intellectual Property Rights Management Plan and Activities – Part A

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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-center clinical trial.

Deliverable D1.3 Description

According to the Grant Agreement (GA), D1.3 “Innovation and IPR management plan and activities - Part A” aims at providing a plan for innovation and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management for the entire project. All the partners are included as providers of inputs. The final version of the deliverable (Part B, delivered on M42) will also include any updates and an outline of related activities during the course of the project. Output of Task 1.4.

In particular, its goal is to define the IPRs (Intellectual Property Rights) management of the project and will be the basis for the exploitation strategy of the Consortium and the relative business model implementation.

The document is structured with an initial definition of IPR-related terms and Process and then goes deeper in the identification of the Key Exploitable Results resulting from the developing of the ThrombUS+ technology as system components and as integrated system.

An updated version of this document will be release at the end of the project (M42).

Cite this Document as

Dionisio P, and the ThrombUS+ Consortium, Innovation and Intellectual Property Rights Management Plan and Activities – Part, Deliverable 1.3, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 31 March 2024.

Terms and Definitions

Term	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CA	Consortium Agreement
CIP	Competitiveness and Innovation Framework Programme
DoA	Description of Action
DVT	Deep Vein Thrombosis
EC	European Commission
EEA	Ethics External Advisor
EEB	External Exploitation Board
EU	European Union
FP7	Framework Programme Seven
GA	General Assembly (when within the context of project management procedure)
GIs	Geographical Indications
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
HealthTech	Health Technology
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IEB	Internal Exploitation Board
IP	Intellectual property
IPR	Intellectual property rights
ISO TC	International Organization for Standardization Technical Committee
SAB	Stakeholders Advisory Board
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TL	Task Leader

Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the activities developed under Task 1.4 Innovation and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management, that aims to identify project results requiring protection, and to define rules of IPRs exploitation.

First activity of this task foresees the identification of the key products and services of the project that will be built around the ThrombUS+ solution. This document will report about the project Key Exploitable Results (KERs) at Month 03 of project implementation detailing in a preliminary way Intellectual the Property Rights (IPR) protection and exploitation for each result and also foreseen Technology Readiness Level (TRL).

Such activities involved the entire consortium for the definition of a ThrombUS+ strategy for the project results exploitation after the project lifespan. A ground basis of IPR analysis has been performed to identify main information regarding the ThrombUS+ exploitation phase.

This analysis provides a solid foundation for the project's IPR management, ensuring that the project's valuable results are appropriately protected and exploited. By defining these rules, the project can secure its long-term sustainability and continue to benefit society.

The D1.3 "Innovation and IPR management plan and activities - Part A" is a crucial deliverable that tackles the important Horizon Europe objectives of integrating technology in service delivery and fostering the development of an HealthTech sector in Europe.

This comprehensive report will examine the significance of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) in the context of innovative HealthTech solutions. It will highlight the potential of IPR management to facilitate seamless integration of technology into service delivery for older adults. Furthermore, the report will explore how a robust IPR framework can promote the growth and sustainability of the HealthTech sector in Europe, encouraging investment, collaboration, and advancement of cutting-edge solutions for elderly care.

This document is a publishable summary of the deliverable.

1. Innovation Management Plan

Innovation management is the process of strategically steering the inception, progression and execution of novel concepts, ultimately transforming ideas with commercial viability into tangible products. Key aspects involve:

- **Idea Generation:** This entails cultivating creativity and fostering the exploration of novel concepts. Techniques such as brainstorming sessions, design thinking workshops, and hackathons serve to ignite innovation.
- **Idea Evaluation and Selection:** Recognizing that not all ideas hold equal potential, innovation management aids in assessing the feasibility, prospective impact, and resource requisites of various concepts to identify those most suitable for further development.
- **Development and Prototyping:** Following the selection of an idea, the focus shifts to refining it into a tangible prototype. This phase facilitates testing, iteration, and feedback collection before advancing to full-scale implementation.
- **Implementation and Commercialization:** This stage marks the realization of innovation, involving the launch of new products, services, or processes into the market and ensuring their successful adoption.
- **Change Management:** Innovation often disrupts existing workflows and procedures. Innovation management assists in effectively navigating this change to mitigate resistance and facilitate a seamless transition for all stakeholders.

In essence, innovation management embodies a methodical approach aimed at optimizing the return on investment (ROI) from novel concepts. It ensures that innovative ideas are not overlooked but rather nurtured and cultivated into valuable assets for the organization.

1.1. Defining innovation

Innovation is the process of creating something new or significantly improving upon existing ideas, products, services, processes, or methods. It entails the application of creativity, problem-solving abilities, and frequently technology to devise solutions that tackle specific needs, hurdles, or opportunities.

Innovation can manifest in different forms:

Product Innovation: This pertains to the creation of new products or the enhancement of existing ones to meet consumer demands or market requirements. Examples include the introduction of cutting-edge gadgets, pharmaceuticals, or vehicles with advanced features.

Process Innovation: This revolves around enhancing the efficiency, effectiveness, or cost-effectiveness of organizational processes. It may involve the adoption of new workflows, automation, or optimization techniques.

Service Innovation: This involves the development of new services or the improvement of existing ones to better cater to customer needs. For instance, the implementation of online banking or ride-sharing services.

Business Model Innovation: This entails redefining how a business operates, generates revenue, or delivers value to customers. Examples include subscription-based models, freemium models, bundling, or razor-blade and more.

Social Innovation: This addresses societal needs or challenges by devising new solutions or approaches. It could encompass initiatives aimed at enhancing healthcare access, improving education quality, or promoting environmental sustainability.

Technological Innovation: This refers to the creation or adoption of new technologies that enable novel solutions or advancements. Examples include breakthroughs in wearables, biomaterials, sensors, artificial intelligence, renewable energy, or biotechnology.

Innovation plays a crucial role in driving economic growth, competitiveness, and societal progress by fostering creativity, driving productivity, and addressing pressing challenges. It often involves collaboration, risk-taking, and a willingness to challenge the status quo.

On top of this and for the sake of the project, the following key documents have been taken into consideration for the assessing of the innovation dimensions of the ThrombUS+ project.

- Innovation as defined by EU https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-07/ec_rtd_factsheet-innovation-principle.pdf
- ISO TC 279 in the standard ISO 56000:2020 defines innovation as "a new or changed entity, realizing or redistributing value".
- New European Innovation Agenda https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/support-policy-making/shaping-eu-research-and-innovation-policy/new-european-innovation-agenda_en#:~:text=The%20New%20European%20Innovation%20Agenda%20%2C%20adopted%20on%205%20July%202022,bring%20them%20on%20the%20market.

1.2. Innovation process

Innovation management is an organic and structured approach composed by specific steps as reported below:

- Identification and dynamic management of the innovation management approach.
- Understanding of the landscape, including market, key stakeholders, trends, technologies, needs and opportunities.
- Continuous monitoring of the landscape.
- Assessment of the innovation potential of research results.
- Liaise with project management and take corrective measures if needed, to ensure that market needs are best met.

The innovation management strategy will be implemented through activities, which are planned in a way that allows their execution in iterations, to ensure they are continuously in line with ongoing evolution in the market.

Activities to implement innovation management include an understanding and continuous monitoring of the medical devices and related domains landscape, in terms of market needs developments and opportunities. This will ensure that project activities remain relevant within the global context and maintain a high degree of innovation.

MEDEA will be the partner responsible for innovation management.

1.3. Innovation management tools – EU Innovation Radar

Innovation management tools are essential for organizations to effectively plan, execute, and monitor their innovation initiatives. These tools help streamline processes, facilitate collaboration, and foster creativity within teams. In the existing landscape of a tools and approaches jungle, the EU Innovation Radar is an initiative of the European Commission focused on the identification of high potential innovations in FP7, CIP

and Horizon 2020 projects¹. It supports innovators by suggesting a range of targeted actions to assist them in fulfilling their potential in the market. This initiative involves: assessing the maturity of innovations developed within projects and identifying high potential innovators and innovations; providing guidance during the project duration in terms of the most appropriate steps to reach the market; and supporting innovators through entrepreneurship initiatives to cover specific needs concerning networking, access to finance, Intellectual Property Rights, etc. The market potential and innovation readiness are among the strongest dimensions of the ICT innovations developed in the projects, while innovation management has room for improvement.

The structured questionnaire that is used to review projects with respect to their innovative output by the EU Innovation Radar can be used in ThrombUS+ to perform an internal qualitative evaluation of the potential innovations developed within the project. This questionnaire will be used to monitor and assess innovation during the project and report regularly at GA and project review meetings.

2. Intellectual Property Rights Management Plan

2.1. Defining IPR

Intellectual property rights (IPR) are legal protections granted to creations of the mind. These creations can be tangible (inventions) or intangible (ideas, designs). Types of intellectual property rights include:

- **Patents:** Protect inventions, new processes, machines, manufactured items, and chemical compositions.
- **Copyrights:** Protect original creative works like literary works, music, software, and artistic works.
- **Trademarks:** Protect distinctive signs and symbols used to identify goods and services from a particular source.
- **Trade Secrets:** Protect confidential information that gives a business a competitive advantage.
- **Industrial Designs:** Industrial designs protect the visual appearance or aesthetic aspects of a product, such as its shape, colour, or surface ornamentation. They prevent others from copying or imitating the design without permission.
- **Geographical Indications:** Geographical indications (GIs) identify products that originate from a specific geographical location and possess qualities, reputation, or characteristics attributable to that location. GIs protect against unauthorized use of the geographical indication on products that do not meet the required standards or criteria.

Intellectual property rights are enforced through legal mechanisms, such as registration, licensing, litigation, and enforcement actions. These rights help creators and inventors monetize their intellectual assets, promote innovation, and stimulate economic growth.

2.2. Intellectual property rights management plan

The ThrombUS+ project employs several processes to identify and monitor its intellectual property rights (IPR). These six processes are listed in detail below and are summarized in Figure 1.

- 1) **Identification:** The project initiates a thorough assessment to identify potential intellectual property within its scope. This involves analysing the project's innovations, technology, software,

¹ De Prato, G., Nepelski, D. and Piroli, G. (2015). Innovation Radar: Identifying Innovations and Innovators with High Potential in ICT FP7, CIP & H2020 Projects. JRC Scientific and Policy Reports – EUR 27314 EN. Seville: JRC-IPTS

designs, and other creative outputs. Additionally, a thorough search within relevant patent databases is foreseen in order to refine the freedom to operate.

- 2) **Monitoring:** The project establishes a system for continuous monitoring of IPR. This involves regularly reviewing and assessing new developments, ensuring that potential infringements or unauthorized use of intellectual property are detected and addressed promptly. Therefore, the involvement of management bodies ensures the professional execution of the project in a manner also reflecting the interests of different commercial partners in the field of the IPR management.
- 3) **Patenting:** ThrombUS+ partners may submit patent applications for its eligible inventions during the project implementation with advance written notice to the Consortium Parties to ensure that the proposed patent application does not infringe upon any existing patents held by the Parties. This process involves engaging qualified patent experts to draft and submit patent applications to relevant intellectual property offices. The project ensures that it adheres to legal requirements and timelines associated with patent filings.

Figure 1. IPR management process.

- 4) **Legal Evaluation:** The project seeks legal evaluation and advice to assess the strength and validity of its intellectual property. This may involve conducting patent searches, prior art analysis, and evaluating the potential for patent infringement. The Legal Evaluation will also include contacting the Parties to the Consortium with the proposed plans to file any patents to ensure that the filings do not infringe on existing patents held by the Parties.
- 5) **Protection Strategies:** ThrombUS+ develops strategies to protect its intellectual property, such as implementing confidentiality agreements, trade secret protection measures, copyright registrations, and other appropriate safeguards.
- 6) **Collaboration and Licensing:** The project explores opportunities for collaboration, licensing, or strategic partnerships that allow for the commercialization and utilization of its intellectual property assets while safeguarding its rights and interests.

By following these processes, the project aims to ensure comprehensive identification, monitoring, and protection of its intellectual property rights, enabling it to capitalize on its innovations and maintain a competitive edge in the market.

3. ThrombUS+ Key Exploitable Results

ThrombUS+ aims to revolutionize the diagnosis and management of deep vein thrombosis (DVT) by developing a comprehensive wearable device that includes the ThrombUS+ strap for wearable continuous ultrasound DVT imaging and the ThrombUS+ sock with embedded sensors for multimodal DVT and activity monitoring, integrated with artificial intelligence and extended reality for automated DVT detection, prevention and patient rehabilitation. This innovative device will enable early detection and accurate assessment of DVT, helping to reduce mortality and the risk of complications and improve patient outcomes.

The major marketable results are

- (1) the ThrombUS+ comprehensive wearable device (including the ThrombUS+ strap and the ThrombUS+ sock components and software);
- (2) the ThrombUS+ strap component; and
- (3) the ThrombUS+ sock component.

Other exploitable outcomes include:

- (4) the accompanying ThrombUS+ app for real-time data analysis, visualization, and personalized management of DVT;
- (5) the AI-based diagnostic algorithms and related dataset per artificial intelligence (AI) model training;
- (6) the platform for DVT risk assessment and patient empowerment; and
- (7) the decision support module for clinical decision-making.

Transforming the developed automated DVT diagnostic ultrasound device prototype and related ThrombUS+ components into a fully commercialized product is expected to take approximately two years, encompassing manufacturing scale-up, regulatory approvals, and market and sales launch activities. The consortium members will collaborate by leveraging their combined expertise. Additionally, the consortium will protect intellectual property through IP audits, patent filings, and ownership and licensing agreements, safeguarding their interests.

4. Management bodies in IPR management

The professional execution of the project in a manner also reflecting the interests of different commercial partners in the field of the IPR management are ensured by management bodies: the **Internal Exploitation Board** and the **External Exploitation Board**.

4.1. The Internal Exploitation Board

The Internal Exploitation Board comprises of representatives from all members the ThrombUS+ consortium. Its role is the continuous assessment of the market, exploitation planning and business model definition (support and liaising to companies, SMEs and other stakeholders).

The Internal Exploitation Board of the ThrombUS+ project plays a vital role in ensuring effective intellectual property rights (IPR) management. This board focuses on monitoring and overseeing all IPR aspects related to the project.

Its primary responsibility is to convene periodic meetings to discuss and evaluate the status of IPR within the project. By doing so, the board ensures that intellectual property is properly protected, managed, and utilized to maximize the project's potential. Through regular monitoring and discussions, the Exploitation Board maintains a proactive approach towards IPR and safeguarding the project's innovations.

4.2. The External Exploitation Board

During the project implementation and according to the status and results achieved, the consortium will consider the need of taking advantage of an External Exploitation Board in order to refine the exploitation approach that will be implemented within the project. The External Exploitation Board (EEB) will comprise of external partners who will provide nonbinding strategic advice, specifically for the exploitation part.

This external board will be defined and agreed among all members of the ThrombUS+ Consortium via a General Assembly discussion and decision when deemed necessary. The members of the board will be selected on the base of their expertise and on the added value they can bring to the project.

The EEB has the following objectives:

- 1) EEB members' activity will be in terms of advices to fine-tune the ThrombUS+ project implementation and impact maximization;
- 2) The members could be also invited to give input/review to the ThrombUS+ deliverables;
- 3) EEB members will not be responsible for any aspects relating to the governance of the project.

5. Conclusions

This deliverable reports the IPR management practices within the ThrombUS+ project. Guidelines and policies are aligned with the original provisions made by the Consortium Agreement and the project Description of Action.